

Xolmirov Begali Abdixamidovich
Study place: (PhD) in TSUL

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LEGAL REGULATION OF ELECTRONIC CURRENCY RELATIONS (CRYPTO CURRENCY)

Annotation: *This article covers the turnover of cryptocurrencies, its features, international practice on regulation, as well as the relations of central banks with respect to cryptocurrencies. In our country, proposals for the regulation of the circulation of cryptocurrencies have been developed.*

Key words: *crypto currencies, bitcoin system, monetary system, institutions of Nobank*

Annotatsiya: *Ушбу мақолада криптовалюталар айланмаси, унинг хусусиятлари, тартибга солиши бўйича халқаро амалиёт, шунингдек, Марказий банкларнинг криптовалюталарга нисбатан муносабатлари ёритилган. Мамлакатимизда криптовалюталар муомаласини тартибга солиши бўйича таклифлар ишлаб чиқилган.*

Калит сўзлар: *криптовалюта, биткоин тизими, пул тизими, нобанк муассасалари*

Аннотация: *В этой статье обсуждается крипто валют, его характеристики, международные регуляторные операции, а также отношение центральных банков к криптовалютам. В нашей стране разработаны предложения по регулированию обращения криптовалют.*

Ключевые слова: *криптовалюты, система биткойнов, денежная система, учреждения Nobank*

Although electronic money (E-money) and their impact on the economy became the central theme of the discussions in the early 1990s, the introduction of electronic money products is rapidly developing at a sufficient rate. Nevertheless, since 2009 Year, innovations related to bitcoin and its underlying block chain technologies have led to an increase in interest in crypto currencies. New generations of electronic currencies, known as digital or virtual currencies, are putting on the agenda pressing issues for central banks, the financial system and the economy as a whole . At the moment, the performance of money in the conditions of the digital economy as a full-fledged monetary function the question is being asked. Cashless society among developed countries building is escalating competition at once. This is, in turn, the block chain technologies, in particular, "mitigate" the attitude towards Bitcoin, electronic active modern technologies aimed at sharpening the scale of payments it is necessary to introduce.

In the article, methods of research such as analysis of selected literature, synthesis, comparison, grouping were used.

Until recently, there were two approaches to limiting the use of crypto currencies: restrictions in the nature of introducing and regulating taxes on operations with

cryptocurrencies. This negatively affected the effective and beneficial use of them in the field of payments. By the autumn of 2015, the situation with the regulation of crypto currency has radically changed after European court decided not to impose Value Added Tax (VAT) on operations with cryptocurrencies. Currently, regulation is the only possibility of carrying out control over the use of cryptocurrencies in the countries of the European Union. Nevertheless, in Europe it is observed to introduce a "soft" mode of regulation instead of Kuchay regulation of the turnover of cryptocurrencies. In the European Union, there is no special law regulating the circulation and use of digital currencies. In October 2012, the European Central Bank prepared a report on the schemes of digital currencies, which included an analysis of the bitcoin system, the legal status of such a system within the framework of the current European legislation. Also, the issue of introducing digital currencies into the scope of the concept of "electronic money", established by the directive on electronic money (2009/10/EU) and regulating them within the framework of this document, has been considered. The report notes that the term bitcoin corresponds to some criteria for equalizing this or that object to electronic money. But the most important thing is that bitcoin does not meet the criteria for the provision of money issued for circulation. In addition, the report notes that the norms of this normative act do not apply to activities and operations related to bitcoin, although there are also opinions that Bitcoin falls within the scope of the impact of the Directorate of payment service estiva (2007/64/EU). In the US states of Florida, California and New York, it is legal to conclude transactions with crypto currencies. By December of the year 2018, Chicago option and commodity exchanges in the US launched futures trading on bitcoin. At the legislative level, the German government recognized bitcoin as a Financial Accounting Unit and a means of mutual settlements. Because, despite the fact that bitcoin is used by local suppliers of goods and services as a monetary asset, since the norms of Legal Regulation were not introduced, they did not pay the income tax on the amount of 25 percent. After the adoption of the relevant law, all transactions related to bitcoin began to be taxed.

In Japan, crypto currency Mt. When Gox met the bankrupt, the government came up with a statement about the importance of taxation and regulation of bitcoin. Nevertheless, practically no measures have been taken regarding the regulation of bitcoin. However, the Japanese government came to April 1 of 2017 year and adopted a legislation that gives bitcoin the status of an official means of payment. In addition to this, a number of regulatory documents have been approved that allow integrating crypto currency into the local banking system. The Swiss government equated Bitcoin with foreign currency. Currently, Switzerland, Gibraltar and Malta are recognized as the most successful jurisdictions for companies working in the field of block chain and cryptocurrencies. In Australia and Singapore, taxes on bitcoin turnover remained. Also, the implementation of operations with crypto currency in Bangladesh is punishable by up to 12 years in the form of imprisonment. Meanwhile, many are interested in the question of whether central banks will also issue their own cryptocurrencies in order to compete with private cryptocurrencies. Therefore, the impact of the central bank on the circulation of digital currencies, its impact on the national economy, in particular on the balances of the Central

bank, Commercial Banks and non-bank financial institutions, is being analyzed in depth by economist scientists, experts and monetary authorities. In particular, some researchers believe that the introduction into circulation can lead to the transformation of aspects of the entire monetary system, with the aim of performing the functions of a cost-free instrument of treatment, a safe savings instrument and a stable unit of account, and on this basis of interest to consumers (Bordeaux, Levin, 2017). In addition, the Bank of England published its research in the field of MBRV to the general public (Kumhof, Clare, 2018) . Within the framework of the study, three models were distinguished. In particular: - financial Institutions access (Model FI) model based on authorization to financial institutions: only banks and non-banking financial institutions will be authorized to use. Banks and non-banking financial institutions can carry out direct cross-transactions on the sale on the basis of the exchange of securities established by the central bank - model based on empowerment for the entire economy (Economy-wide Access (Model EW)) : together with banking and non-banking financial institutions, households and businesses will also have access. This means that performs a monetary function for all agents in the economy. In this model, too, only banks and non-banking financial institutions are authorized to carry out operations on the sale with the central bank, while households and enterprises will be able to convert their tokens into through exchanges. It is also possible for households and enterprises to exchange among themselves. - financial institutions plus narrow banking authority model (Financial Institutions Plus CBDC-Backed Narrow Bank Access (Model FI+)) provided with MBRV: banks and non-banking financial institutions will be entitled to use MBRV. Within the financial institutions of Nobank, at least one of them performs a narrow range of banking functions and serves to provide households and enterprises with financial assets provided with MBRV. In our opinion, the question of how much the digital currency that will be released into circulation by the central bank will practically improve the functions of money should be thoroughly studied and analyzed. In particular, attention should be paid to the increase in efficiency and security through the emission of future generations of Digital-looking banknotes, which include the latest convenience of technological development . In this place, it is required to eliminate anonymity in the ecosystem of the block chain, in particular, the use of supervised Machine Learning, etc. on a controlled or controlled machine.

In Uzbekistan, important steps are being taken to strengthen the regulatory and legal framework for the formation of the digital economy. In particular, the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan № PP-3832 "on measures for the development of the digital economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated July 3, 2018 was adopted, in accordance with which the authorized body in the field of introduction and development of the digital economy was established, the issues of turnover of crypto-assets and its regulation It is noteworthy that the turnover of crypto-assets in our country was regulated by special regulatory legal acts. In addition, operations related to the turnover of crypto-assets of legal entities and individuals, including operations carried out by non-residents, are not considered as taxable objects, while revenues from these operations are not included in the taxable base on taxes and other mandatory payments. Also, the norms of the

legislation on the regulation of the currency for exchange operations related to the turnover of crypto-assets, conducted by persons who received licenses in accordance with the established procedure for carrying out activities in the sphere of turnover of crypto-assets, are not applied. In accordance with the resolution of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 28, 2020 "on measures for the wide introduction of the digital economy and e-government"PP-4699, the ministry for the development of information technologies and communications of the Republic of Uzbekistan has been established as an authorized body in the field of digital economy .

Meanwhile, at the National Agency for Project Management under the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the powers for the introduction of crypto-assets and block chine technology were preserved. For the first time in the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan № PF-5296 "on measures to radically improve the activities of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan" on September 9, 2018, the term "digital bank" was used. In accordance with the amendments and additions to the regulation of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on the procedure for registration of banks and licensing of their activities"by the decision of the management of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 30, 2018 № 22/5, "digital bank-is a bank or its structural division providing Remote rendering of banking services by digital banks is carried out taking into account the requirements of legislation in accordance with the rules of internal procedures of the bank. The Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued a statement for the first time on crypto-currencies in September 2017. He noted that as a result of the widespread use of crypto currencies in the implementation of anonymous transactions, a wide path to illegal money transfers and fraud is being opened, which in some countries contributes to the further growth of the hoofing economy. In addition, the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan does not provide for the implementation of payment or other operations using crypto currencies.

The rapid growth of digital transformation processes, the wide introduction of digital technologies into the management of business processes, the increase in the types and scope of digital assets ultimately leads to an increase in demand for digital currencies. In addition, the use of digital currencies contributes to the effective functioning of the ecosystem of the digital economy by providing new opportunities that Fiat money can not provide. Therefore, the liberalization of the system of regulation of crypto currencies, the definition of the scope of the use of crypto assets in the event of the provision of crypto ability, and its access to it in the near future will become a trend that occurs not only in developed, but also in developing countries. In our opinion, even in our country, when forming a system of regulation of cryptocurrencies, it is considered worthwhile to carry out the following:

1. The legal basis of operations with cryptocurrencies should be strengthened by the relevant law and the areas of use of cryptocurrencies in our country should be strictly defined.

2. The central bank should assess the impact of the use of cryptocurrencies on the demand for money in the country, take into account changes in the volume of investments in crypto actives in the management of the money mass.

3. It is necessary that the central bank develop a strategy for the circulation of digital currencies based on the requirements of the digital economy. it is necessary to cover the areas of application of the digital currency of the Central Bank, the characteristics of the quality of the investment asset, the definition of the circle of participants with the authority to use it, the issues of restriction if necessary.

4. In a harmonic manner to the increase in the share of the digital economy, crypto actives should take measures to introduce leading crypto currencies into the composition of official international currency reserves due to their profitability.

5. It is necessary for the central bank to take part in the market of crypto-currencies and to prevent their impact on market liquidity, in particular, the implementation of swap operations with crypto currencies. It should also be considered the development of the futures market of crypto currencies, that is, operations with derivative financial instruments (derivatives), the underlying asset of which are crypto currencies.